

EFFECT OF COOLING RATE ON STATIC, LOW ENERGY IMPACT AND FATIGUE PERFORMANCE OF A COMMINGLED E-GLASS/POLYPROPYLENE COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY: The purpose of this experimental work was to determine the effect of cooling rate on tensile, flexural, low energy impact and tension-tension fatigue performance of a woven glass fabric reinforced polypropylene composite, compression molded from commingled glass/polypropylene fibers. It was shown that except for the low energy impact properties, all other mechanical properties considered are significantly affected by cooling rate.

KEYWORDS: Commingled E-glass/polypropylene fabric, compression molding, cooling rates, tensile strength, flexural strength, energy absorption, fatigue strength.

INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic matrix composites have a great potential in the automotive industry, since they can be molded or formed in cycle times that are much shorter than the cycle times required for thermosetting matrix composites. There are also other advantages of thermoplastic matrix composites that are important to the automotive industry. For example, thermoplastic matrix composites can be joined and repaired by fusion welding. They can also be recycled, which is an important consideration for the life cycle analysis of automotive materials. In recent years, several publications have appeared in the literature exploring the processing characteristics of thermoplastic matrix composites containing glass or carbon fibers in polypropylene, polyamide or thermoplastic polyester matrix [1-5]. The principal reason for considering these materials is that they are relatively inexpensive compared to carbon fiber reinforced PEEK or PPS that are commonly considered for aerospace applications, and thus they have a better opportunity to be used in automotive or other non-aerospace applications.

Compression molding is one of the most common processing methods used for making thermoplastic matrix composite parts. Three principal steps in this process are heating, pressing or flow forming and cooling. All three of these steps will influence the productivity, quality performance of the compression molded part. In this study, we will consider the effect of cooling rate on the tensile, flexural, low energy impact and fatigue performance of a commingled E-glass fiber/polypropylene woven fabric composite.

EXPERIMENTAL

Material

Commingled woven glass fabric reinforced polypropylene was selected as the material for this study. Twintex Inc. provided several 2.36-mm thick hard flat sheets of this material. The sheets were black in color due to the addition of carbon black, which is commonly used for UV protection. The fabric configuration in the sheets was balanced. The nominal glass fiber content was 60% by weight. Several plates were compression molded from these sheets using either 1 or 2 layers.

Compression Molding

A 30-ton hydraulic press was used to compression mold woven fabric plates in an aluminum mold with the cavity dimensions of 216 mm x 122 mm. The ply areal dimensions were 208 mm (length) x 114 mm (width). Both these dimensions were 8 mm less than the cavity dimensions to allow for the material flow during compression molding. Spacer blocks were used to control the molded plate thickness. The mold temperature was 220°C, which was 55°C higher than the melting point of polypropylene. Two different molding pressures were used, namely, 1.37 and 3 MPa. After placing the fabric stack in the mold at room temperature, the press platens were closed and the heating cycle was started. The desired pressure was applied after both platen temperatures reached 200°C. When the platen temperatures reached 220°C, the cooling stage was started; however, the pressure was maintained until the platen temperatures were close to room temperature. The cooling rate was controlled by either completely or partially opening the water valves. In addition, slow cooling was used in which the temperature controllers were simply turned off and the molded plate was allowed to cool down to room temperature in the press under pressure. Fast/slow cooling was achieved by opening the water valves until the temperature of the plate reached 135 °C and then turning off the temperature controllers. The cooling times and average cooling rates for the various cooling conditions considered were: (a) Fast: cooling time = 12 minutes, cooling rate = 15 °C/min, (b) Medium Fast: cooling time = 24 minutes, cooling rate = 7.5 °C/min, (c) Fast/Slow: cooling time = 540 minutes, cooling rate = 15 /0.0036 °C/min, and, (d) Slow: cooling time = 840 minutes, cooling rate = 0.0036 °C/min. It was observed that the slowly cooled plates had numerous surface pits, whereas the fast cooled plates had a relatively smooth surface without any visible surface pits.

Table 1: Molding Conditions

No. of Layers	Pressure (MPa)	Cooling Rate (°C/min)	Plate Thickness (mm)	Tests Performed
1	3	15 (Fast)	1.78	Flexural
		0.0036 (Slow)	2.16	
2	1.37	15 (Fast)	3.75	Flexural
	3	15 (Fast)	3.73	
	3	15 (Fast)	3.5	Tension, Impact, Fatigue
		7.5 (Med. Fast)	3.5	
		15/0.0036 (Fast/Slow)	3.5	
0.0036 (Slow)	3.5			

Mechanical Tests

Four different mechanical tests were conducted, namely tension tests, 3-point flexural tests, low energy impact tests and tension-tension fatigue tests. All these tests were performed at room temperature (approximately 23°C).

(a) Tension and Fatigue Tests

Both tension and fatigue tests were performed on dog-bone shaped specimens of the type shown in Fig. 1. The specimens were prepared by first cutting rectangular strips on a water-cooled diamond saw, and then shaping them on a high-speed router. The edges of the specimens were cleaned using 100-grit sandpaper. The specimens were clamped in the MTS testing machine at a specified grip separation and pulled until failure. The crosshead speed in tension tests was 10 mm/min. The fatigue tests were conducted on the MTS testing machine in tension-tension load-controlled sinusoidal cycling mode. The maximum cyclic load was 70%, 60%, 50% and 40% of the tensile strength. The ratio of the minimum load and the maximum load, called the R-ratio, was 0.1. The frequency of cycling was 10 Hz. The fatigue tests were continued until failure or up to 2×10^6 cycles, whichever occurred first. The load-displacement hysteresis loops were recorded at pre-selected number of cycles during the fatigue tests.

Fig. 1: Tensile and fatigue test specimen (All dimensions are in mm)

(b) Flexural Tests

Three-point flexural tests were conducted on an Instron testing machine using 102 mm long straight-sided beam specimens of rectangular cross section. The specimens were cut parallel (L) to and perpendicular (W) to the length direction of the molded plates. The specimen width was 12 mm. The flexural specimen was supported on two 6.35-mm diameter pins and was loaded at the mid-length using a 6.35-mm diameter pin. The distance between the two supports was 89 mm. The crosshead speed was 10 mm/min.

(b) Low Energy Impact Tests

The low velocity impact tests were conducted on a Dynatup 9210 drop-weight impact testing machine using square specimens, 70 mm x 70 mm in size. The specimen was freely supported on a steel support fixture and impacted with a steel tup containing a 12.7-mm diameter hemispherical end. The outer dimensions of the steel support were 114 mm; however it contained a 50.8-mm diameter central opening, thus creating a simply supported circular plate type configuration for the impacted plates. The tup weight was 62.98 N. The tup velocities recorded by the velocimeter just before impacting the plate were 2.41, 2.98 and 3.44 m/s, and the corresponding input impact energies were approximately 18.64, 28.51 and 37.99 J. The load-time and energy-time plots were recorded at 0.0061 ms time intervals using the Impulse data acquisition software.

RESULTS

Tensile Properties

Fig. 2 shows the stress-displacement diagrams for specimens molded at different cooling rates. All the stress-displacement diagrams were nonlinear and the failure modes were very similar. As shown in Table 2, cooling rate had a significant effect on tensile modulus as well as tensile strength of the specimens. Both modulus and strength had the maximum values at the fast cooling rate and decreased with decreasing cooling rate. Davies and Cantwell [5] reported similar effect of cooling rate on the tensile properties of commingled glass fabric/PP composites.

Fig. 2: Tensile stress-displacement diagrams

Table 2: Tensile Properties

Cooling Rate (°C/min)	Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)
15 (Fast)	13.45	300.8
7.5 (Med. Fast)	12.5	254.4
15/0.0036 (Fast/Slow)	12.1	227.5
0.0036 (Slow)	9.4	182.2

Flexural Properties

Table 3 lists the average flexural modulus and flexural strength of three specimens for each molding condition. The following observations can be made from the flexural test results.

- Lower molding pressure produced higher modulus and higher strength.
- For the same molding pressure, fast cooling produced a slightly higher modulus and strength.

Table 2: Flexural Properties

No. of Layers	Pressure (MPa)	Cooling Rate (°C/min)	Thickness (mm)	Span to Thickness Ratio	Direction ⁽¹⁾	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	Flexural Strength (MPa)
2	3	15 (Fast)	3.73	23.6	L	10.2	186.5
					W	11.4	204.3
2	1.37	15 (Fast)	3.75	23.4	L	12.8	231.5
					W	13.0	223.3
1	3	15 (Fast)	2.16	40.7	L	10.4	205.3
					W	10.6	215.6
1	3	0.0036 (Slow)	2.16	40.7	L	9.6	184.9
					W	10.0	143.3

(1) L and W are the length and width directions of the mold.

Impact Properties

In the impact tests, the tup did not penetrate through any of the specimens tested; instead it rebounded off after reaching the maximum travel, which coincided with the maximum deflection of the specimen. Fig. 3 shows the typical load-deflection diagram obtained in impact tests. Table 4 shows the impact test results in terms of the peak load, deflection at the peak load and the energy absorbed. From this table, it appears that none of these impact parameters were affected by the cooling rate.

Fig. 3: Load-deflection diagrams obtained in low-energy impact tests (Incident Impact Velocity = 2.41 m/s)

There was visible damage on both the impacted as well as the unimpacted sides of the plates subjected to low energy impact tests. The impacted side had a dent at the impact point and the severity of the dent was observed to be less with decreasing cooling rate. Similarly, the visible damage on the unimpacted side also was less at lower cooling rates. The interior damage of the impacted plates was investigated using a scanning electron microscope. Fiber fracture was clearly visible at the edge of the dent. In some cases, cracks were observed starting from large voids that acted as stress concentration (Fig. 4). On the unimpacted surface, longitudinal fiber failure and matrix cracking in the transverse fiber bundle was observed. No delamination was observed in any of the impacted specimens examined.

Table 4: Results of Low-Energy Impact Tests (Plate Thickness = 3.55 mm)

Cooling Rate (°C/min)	Impact Velocity (m/s)	Impact Energy (J)	Peak Load (N)	Deflection at Peak Load (mm)	Energy Absorbed (J)
15 (Fast)	2.41	18.64	5.87	6.24	12.86
	2.98	28.51	6.92	7.30	21.88
	3.44	37.99	7.65	7.98	31.45
7.5 (Medium Fast)	2.41	18.64	5.93	6.18	13.10
	2.98	28.51	6.78	7.53	22.22
	3.44	37.99	7.54	7.89	31.74
15/0.0036 (Fast/Slow)	2.41	18.64	5.93	6.05	13.34
	2.98	28.51	6.68	7.56	22.17
	3.44	37.99	7.96	8.27	34.13
0.0036 (Slow)	2.41	18.64	5.57	6.50	13.98
	2.98	28.51	6.57	7.67	22.86
	3.44	37.99	6.94	7.80	33.21

Fig. 4: Cracks originating from void in the matrix in an impacted plate

Fatigue Properties

Fig. 5 shows the fatigue test results. The vertical axis in this figure is the ratio of the maximum cyclic stress and the tensile strength and the horizontal axis is the fatigue life expressed in terms

of number of cycles to failure. As expected, the fatigue life increased with decreasing stress-to-strength ratio. The cooling rate had a very significant effect on fatigue life. However, unlike the tensile strength, the slow-cooled specimens performed the best in tension-tension fatigue tests and the fast-cooled specimens had the poorest fatigue performance.

Fig. 5: Maximum fatigue stress to tensile strength ratio vs. number of fatigue cycles at different cooling rates (Fast: 15, Medium Fast: 7.5, Fast/Slow: 15/0.0036 and Slow: 0.0036 °C/min)

During fatigue tests, gradual softening or loss in stiffness occurred due to the appearance of microscopic damages long before the appearance of any visible damage. This is shown in Fig. 6. The specimen stiffness in this study was measured using the slope of the hysteresis loop, which was recorded during the fatigue test. Fig. 6 also shows that the higher the stress level, the larger the stiffness reduction. Furthermore, the faster the cooling rate, the larger the stiffness reduction. Fig. 7 shows photographs of several failed fatigue specimens. All of these specimens failed in the gage area. The macroscopic failure modes were similar in each of these specimens. There was evidence of delamination, fiber fracture as well as matrix cracking.

Fig. 6: Stiffness ratio vs. number of cycles at different stress levels and cooling rates

Fig. 7: Appearance of specimens after fatigue tests (From top to bottom: Fast, Medium Fast, Fast/Slow, Slow)

CONCLUSIONS

Mechanical properties of commingled woven glass fiber reinforced polypropylene matrix composite were studied in this paper. The principal compression molding parameter considered was the cooling rate, although limited number of experiments were conducted in which the molding pressure was varied at two levels. It was observed that in both the flexural and tension tests, fast cooling produced higher modulus and higher strength, whereas lower molding pressure produced higher flexural modulus and higher flexural strength. In low energy impact tests, there was no significant effect of cooling rate on the maximum load and the energy absorbed. However, the slow-cooled plates appeared to sustain less visible impact damage. Cooling rate had a significant effect on the fatigue performance. The fast-cooled specimens produced the lowest fatigue performance, whereas the slow cooled specimens produced the best fatigue performance.

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